

Electronic supplements to: 'Evolutionary–phylogenetic pathway of the Cretaceous ammonite genus *Aegocrioceras* and its relationship to *Juddiceras* spp. and *Crioceratites* spp.'

Papers in Palaeontology

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1 Superimposition procedure

Fig. S1. Schematic representation of the superimposition procedure of ammonite conchs used in this study. A specimen for superimposition is aligned with the base specimen through rotation and radial angle values are adjusted accordingly. For details of the procedure, see Hoffmann *et al.* (2019).

Fig. S2. Alignment of the landmark points of the ammonite specimens. The black line indicates the base specimen (Specimen 88.2) against which the other specimens were aligned. A: *Aegocrioceras* spp. specimens from the clay pit Resse (mean deviance: 28.96). B: Specimens of the outgroup species.

2 Additional results

2.1 Morphology of *Aegocrioceras* spp.

Fig. S3. Bivariate distribution of the absolute rib index (ARI₄₀) in *Aegocrioceras* spp. from the clay pit Resse.

2.2 Phylogeny of *Aegocrioceras* spp.

A

B

Fig. S4. Unrooted phenetic reconstructions of *Aegocrioceras* spp. from the clay pit Resse. A: Simple phylogeny based on the mean morphology of each species. B: Consensus phylogeny, where all morphological parameters for *Aegocrioceras* spp. were allowed to vary randomly around the mean, following a Gaussian distribution with the standard deviation estimated from the data, during 999 random replications. The consensus tree was then calculated on the basis of the Robinson–Foulds distance (Robinson & Foulds 1981). The *Aegocrioceras* clade is printed with bold lines in each case.

Fig. S5. Metric multidimensional scaling (MDS; Gower 1966) of our randomized trees using the information-theoretic metric from Smith (2020). A: The position of our average tree and the median tree amongst the replicates is indicated. B: Correlation between tree distances in MDS space and original distances between trees.

Fig. S6. Tanglegram-comparison between the phylogenetic reconstructions of *Aegocrioceras* spp. from the clay pit Resse, based on either *Juddiceras curvicosta* or *Crioceratites* sp. as the outgroup. Corresponding tree leaves are connected by lines, red lines mark common subtrees present in both phylograms. Scales below trees indicate the Robinson-Foulds distance of the leaves. The trees are nearly identical, with a Baker's Gamma of 0.614 ($p = 0.052$; Baker 1974).

Fig. S7. Phenotypic reconstruction of remaining conch-morphological traits in *Aegocrioceras* spp. from the clay pit Resse and related species (rooted with *Crioceratites* sp.), using the fastAnc-maximum likelihood algorithm (Revell 2012). A: Size of the absolute rib index (ARI₂₀); B: Ontogenetic trajectory of the ARI₂₀; C: Umbilical width index (UWI) size; D: Ontogenetic trajectory of the UWI; E: Ontogenetic trajectory of the whorl expansion rate.

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